

IMPORTANCE OF MATHEMATICS IN COMPUTER SCIENCE

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What is the importance of mathematics in computer science?

Mathematics has probably been the bane of many students' lives (including mine!!!) since its inception. On the other hand, computer science is very interesting, and students study it in the hope of becoming the next programming prodigy!!! Is computer science really that simple?!! No, my friends, this is not true... Computer science is actually closely related to mathematics.

Over the years, there has been much debate about the importance of mathematics in computer science.

Some consider it to be a slight extension of computer science, others believe it is (mostly!) based on computer science. According to Oxford University:

Why is mathematics so important in computer science?

Imagine the Burj Khalifa (the tallest building in the world). So what's the most important thing about this building? No, it's not about the height (well, that too!), but mainly about its foundation. If the Burj Khalifa did not have a strong foundation, it would have swayed violently and fallen harder than it stood!!

So, if you're interested in this off-topic story, mathematics is the foundation of computer science. In fact, we can say that computer science is a part of mathematical sciences in general.

How so? Well, below are some points that illustrate this:

1. Discrete mathematics - the basis of computer science

Have you heard of logical notation, set theory, combinatorics, graph theory, probability theory, number theory, algebra, etc.?

Don't be discouraged, it's all part of discrete mathematics, as well as the basics of programming and computer science (i.e. you should study them for computer science!!!). An example of this is algebra. Logical algebra is used in logic gates and relational algebra is used in

databases. If you need another example, number theory has many applications in cryptography and cryptanalysis.

2. Mathematics teaches you how to use algorithms.

Algorithms are a fundamental part of computer science, and you've probably heard of them one way or another (if not... you need to learn more!!!). Essentially, it is a program or set of instructions that directs the execution of a program.

So where did you first apply the algorithm? It wasn't a computer science lesson, it was a math lesson! Don't believe me?!! So, “ $2 + 3 = 5$ ” is the basic algorithm you learned in math class that shows the sum of 2 and 3. Mathematics is essential for learning the basics of using advanced algorithms in computer science.

3. Mathematics provides essential analytical skills in computer science.

Analytical skills are required for problem solving and data analysis. And think about where you first applied these skills? Mathematics!!! Yes, mathematics always forces you to analyze your equations and understand the derivative process in case of errors. This error must be corrected to obtain a final solution.

This will give you a lot of analytical skills that you can later use to find and fix errors!!! Although there are modern tools that can do this automatically, the experience and knowledge gained from developing and debugging programs is invaluable.

So yes... Computer science is based on mathematics. And if you want to succeed in any computer science, you better develop a love for mathematics because it will help you a lot.

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INTERNET RESOURCES

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